

Commitment to Mediate the Influence of Interpersonal Skills and Competence on Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study was to determine the effect of: (1) Interpersonal Skills on Employee Performance, (2) Competence on Employee Performance, (3) Commitment to Mediate Interpersonal Skills on Employee Performance, and (4) Commitment to Mediate Competency on Employee Performance and used saturated samples.

The population of respondents in this study were non-PNS permanent education staff at the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment, Airlangga University. The number of respondents used was 57 permanent non-PNS education staff. Primary data collection was carried out using a question instrument which was distributed to respondents. The data analysis technique in this study uses Partial Least Square (PLS)

The results of the study concluded that: (1) Interpersonal Skills have a significant effect on Employee Performance, (2) Competence has a significant effect on Employee Performance, (3) Commitment to Mediate on Interpersonal Skills has a non-significant effect on Employee Performance, and (4) Commitment to Mediate on Competence has a non-significant effect on Employee Performance.

KEYWORDS: Interpersonal Skills, Competence, Commitment and Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

Employees are assets that are needed for institutions, because their performance greatly affects the effectiveness of company performance. Therefore, improving employee performance is the main focus of the human resource management unit. They try to develop the potentials possessed by individuals so that they are motivated to make the best contribution to achieving company goals (Azizi et al. 2021). Every organization is formed to be able to achieve its goals. To be able to achieve organizational goals, qualified and high-performance human resources are needed (Suriyanto, 2021). In addition, it is expected to be able to determine the vision and mission of the organization clearly, be able to read the direction of globalization and translate it into various strategies to accelerate the achievement of organizational goals (Sinaga, 2020).

Researchers chose non-PNS education staff as research objects due to two reasons, namely: 1) In 2018 Airlangga University could not propose a change in the status of education staff and teaching staff to become PNS; 2) Every year there are civil servants entering retirement age; 3) Increased work while being non-PNS permanent education staff; 4) Non PNS permanent education personnel have the same rights and obligations as PNS educational staff.

Performance measurements carried out in 2020 use the logbook. Non PNS permanent education staff fill out diaries that can be accessed via gadget on the page uacc.unair.ac.id. In the logbook, non-PNS permanent education staff input what is done every day, upload photos or assignment letters. The results of the assessment in the form of points from the logbook of non-PNS permanent education staff cannot be informed to the direct supervisor. Assessment of direct superiors in the logbook is in the form of approving or disapproving the work of non-PNS permanent education staff every month and is carried out at the end of the month. Related to the absence of permanent non-PNS education staff, filling in the logbook and employee attendance is confirmed manually, meaning that the direct supervisor inquires directly about the presence of non-PNS education staff.

Meanwhile, the performance appraisal conducted in 2022 is an improvement to the existing performance appraisal system. The performance evaluation in question is that the points received can be reduced if non-PNS permanent education staff have problems with employee attendance.

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Source: Directorate of Human Resources (processed)

Diagram 1. Percentage of Achievement of 2020-2022 Performance

From the diagram above, it is found that the percentage of performance achievements in 2020 to 2021 has the same value because it still uses the logbook. The year 2022 already uses an enhanced application. In this renewal application, direct supervisors can find out the points generated by non-PNS permanent education staff and the attendance data for non-PNS permanent education staff is directly integrated when conducting performance appraisals. Performance evaluation obtained from the results of several questions regarding university policies, teamwork, work results report to direct superiors.

In 2022 the highest percentage of performance achievements (100%) is for general administrators while the lowest percentage (95%) is for printing officers. This happens because the work of the general administration can be completed every day, while the printing officer's work will be completed if there is approval from the user and is considered complete if the user has accepted. The trend that occurred in 2020-2022 was a decrease in points for office and building maintenance administrator positions, financial data managers, drivers, security officers, and office assistants. This was due to performance appraisal not only based on logbooks but also teamwork. The non-PNS permanent education staff's performance has not been maximized from the specified target, which results in a decrease in performance related to interpersonal skills, competence and commitment. The problem of the presence of non-PNS permanent education staff is one of the variables that reduces performance appraisal. The assessment of non-PNS permanent education staff for smoking activities on campus is included in the performance appraisal.

The competencies obtained are obtained from training organized by the Directorate of Human Resources related to the field of work of these non-PNS permanent education workers with BNSP certification or equivalent certificates. The table above shows that not all positions have received maximum training. This is constrained by the implementation time and costs required if the output required is a BNSP certified university or equivalent. From the results of an interview with the Head of Human Resources Development Sub-Directorate: "... training this year will be conducted and the data that comes to us is training on OBS for Office Scouts for other training we will discuss with the HR Director" (www/Ali Sahab/01022023) .

grand theory used by the researcher according to Storey (1995) HRM is a distinctive approach to employee management that seeks to achieve competitive advantage through strategic development of capable and highly committed employees using an integrated set of cultural, structural and personnel techniques. With high commitment, maximum performance is achieved in synergy with the vision and mission of the institution.

The work carried out by Airlangga University through the Directorate of Human Resources is to give awards to non-PNS permanent education staff. This award will be given in 2022 during the Airlangga University Anniversary. . Based on the phenomena that exist in an effort to encourage the improvement of the performance of non-PNS permanent education staff in the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment, extracting the interpersonal skills and competence values of non-PNS permanent education staff in carrying out their duties by fostering a high commitment to work so that it is expected to encourage improving the performance of educational staff which results in increased organizational performance.

II. THEORETICAL BASIS

Human Resource Management This is simply the utilization of employee expertise in accordance with the areas controlled and placing them in the right position. So that later it is expected that employees who are placed in a position can play a maximum role in carrying out the agreed duties and responsibilities.

Human resource management is a procedure for managing human beings in an organization so that they can play an effective and efficient role. Management consists of six (6M) elements, namely: Men, Monet Method, Materials, Machines, and Market. The human element (Men) developed into a field of management science called human resource management. The following is the opinion of experts on the notion of human resource development Arifin, (2005): 1) According to Armstrong (1994),

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how people can be managed in the best way in the interests of the organization; 2) According to Keenoy (1990), HRM is a method of maximizing the results of employee resources by integrating HRM into business strategy; 3) According to Storey (1995), HRM is a distinctive approach to employee management that seeks to achieve competitive advantage through the development of strategies from capable and highly committed employees using integrated cultural arrangements, structural and personnel techniques. With the definition put forward by these experts, it shows the importance of human resource management in achieving corporate, employee and community goals.

Interpersonal Skills

In general, human skills can be classified into two, namely technical skills (hard skills) and skills in managing oneself and others (soft skills). Soft skills are basically personal skills, namely special skills that are non-technical, intangible, and personality that determine a person's strengths as a leader, (good) listener, negotiator, and conflict mediator. Meanwhile, hard skills are technical in nature and are usually just written on someone's bio data or CV which includes education, experience, and level of expertise (technical). Soft skills can also be said as interpersonal skills such as the ability to communicate and work together in a group. According Prasetyo (2016) that interpersonal skills (interpersonal skills) are skills to recognize and respond appropriately to the feelings, attitudes and behavior, motivations and desires of others. How we are able to build harmonious relationships by understanding and responding to humans or other people is part of interpersonal skills. indicators selected according to Gardner, (1993) and Buhrmester, D., F. W., Wittenberg & Reis, (1998), among others: 1) Ability to be open; 2) Tolerance towards others; 3) Collaboration with others; 4) Ability to provide support to others; 5) Ability to be assertive; 6) Communicate effectively with others; 7) Ability to manage conflict Competence

Definition of competence according to Elly Romys et al (2022) is the power (authority) to determine/decide a matter. Employee competence is a set of knowledge and skills that must be owned by employees to improve work ability. Competence possessed by employees must be accounted for based on their professional planning, ability to deal with work environment situations, ability to self-manage and ability to improve and develop their knowledge. Competence is an important part that must be owned by an employee in order to carry out the job well (Ardiansyah, Yusuf 2018). The indicators selected for this study are from Wiguna (2017) and Busro (2018), among others: 1) Value; 2) Self-development; 3) Knowledge; 4) Expertise; 5) Professionals

Commitment

The definition of commitment according to Wiener (1982) is organizational commitment defined as encouragement from within the individual to do something in order to support the success of the organization in accordance with the goals and prioritize the interests of the organization. Each employee has a different basis and behavior based on the organizational commitment they have. Employees with high affective commitment have a close emotional attachment to the organization. Means that the individual has the motivation and desire to contribute meaningfully to the organization. Meanwhile, employees with normative commitment give rise to feelings of obligation to employees to repay what has been received from the agency. For employees who have a continuing commitment, they will stay in the organization not for emotional reasons but because they have an inner awareness of the big loss if they leave the organization. The indicators selected for this study from Meyer and Allen, Cut Zurnali, and Steers include: 1) Normative Commitment; 2) Engagement; 3) Continuous Commitment

Employee Performance

Performance reflects the company's ability to manage and allocate its resources, so performance is an important thing that must be achieved by every company, according to Pranogyo et al. (2021) performance can be said as a set of measurements and the value of the results achieved as well as the integrity of the behavior used to do the job. Performance appraisal is basically a key factor for developing an organization effectively and efficiently, due to better policies or programs for existing human resources in the organization. Individual performance appraisal is very useful for the dynamics of organizational growth as a whole, through this assessment it can be seen the actual conditions of how employees are performing. The indicators selected for this research are from Silaen, (2021), Linda Koopmans, and Robbins, (2016) among others: 1) Work Quantity; 2) Quality of Work; 3) Efficient; 4) Punctuality; 5) Initiative; 6) Quality; and 7) Creative

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III. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Information:

- Direct influence
- - - - -→ Indirect influence

IV. HYPOTHESIS

- H1. Interpersonal Skill (X1) has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance with a path coefficient of 0.236 where p-values = 0.044 smaller than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H1 is accepted;
- H2. Competence (X2) has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance with a path coefficient of 0.543 where p-values = 0.000 smaller than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H2 is accepted;
- H3. Interpersonal Skill (X1) has a non significant effect on employee performance through commitment with a path coefficient of 0.059 where p-values = 0.355 greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H3 is rejected;
- H4. Competence (X2) has a non-significant effect on Employee Performance through Commitment with a path coefficient of 0.060 where p-values = 0.260 greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H4 is rejected

V. RESEARCH METHOD

Data Types and Sources

The research method used in this study used primary data in the form of questionnaires which were distributed to 57 permanent non-PNS staff at the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment, Universitas Airlangga with a saturated sample.

Data collection technique

Data collection techniques used using questionnaires, observation and bibliography. The scale used uses a Likert scale of 1-5

Data analysis

This study uses a quantitative approach in its analytical techniques. This approach is supported by structural equation modeling (SEM). The structural equation model uses a statistical tool, namely PLS (partial least squares) in knowing the relationship between the variables.

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Outer Model - Validity Test

The validity test was carried out to determine the ability of the research instrument to measure what should be measured (Haryono, 2016). The reliability test is used to measure the consistency of a measuring instrument in measuring a concept or it can also be used to measure the consistency of respondents in answering question items in questionnaires or research instruments. The loading score parameter is in the research model (Rule of Thumbs > 0.7) and uses the AVE parameter. The AVE score must be above 0.5. If the loading score is < 0.5, this indicator can be removed from the construct because this indicator is not loaded into the construct that represents it.

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Table 1. Validity Testing Based on Factor Loading

Variable	Indicator	Loading Factor	Information
Interpersonal Skills (X1)	X1.1	0.671	Valid
	X1.2	0.722	Valid
	X1.3	0.589	Valid
	X1.4	0.820	Valid
Competency (X2)	X2.1	0.725	Valid
	X2.2	0.767	Valid
	X2.3	0.518	Valid
	X2.4	0.706	Valid
	X2.5	0.774	Valid
Commitment (Z)	Z1	0.915	Valid
	Z2	0.881	Valid
Performance (Y)	Y1	0.550	Valid
	Y2	0.606	Valid
	Y3	0.734	Valid
	Y4	0.625	Valid
	Y5	0.658	Valid

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on table 2, the loading factor for the Interpersonal Skill variable indicator (X1), X1.1 = 0.671; X1.2 = 0.722; X1.3 = 0.589; X1.4 = 0.820 > 0.5 then meets convergent validity. The results of the analysis in the table above show that all indicators in the research variables, namely Interpersonal Skill, Competence, Commitment and Employee Performance variables, have a loading factor > 0.5 (Hair et al., 2013), so these indicators fulfill the validity of the loading value. So all indicators that have passed the validity test based on the second order loading factor can be used as a measure of the variable.

Outer Model – AVE

Table 2. Validity Test Based on Average Variance Extracted

Variable	Indicator	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Information
Interpersonal Skills	Ability to be open (X1.1)	0.597	Valid
	Tolerance towards others (X1.2)		
	Collaborate with others (X1.3)		
	Ability to provide support to others (X1.4)		
Competence	Value (X2.1)	0.596	Valid
	Self-development (X2.2)		
	Knowledge (X2.3)		
	Skills (X2.4)		
	Professional (X2.5)		
Commitment	Normative commitment (Z1)	0.806	Valid
	Engagement (Z2)		
Performance	Working quantity (Y1)	0.541	Valid
	Quality of work (Y2)		
	Efficient (Y3)		
	Timeliness (Y4)		
	Initiative (Y5)		

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The measurement model is the average variance extracted (AVE) value, namely the value indicating the magnitude of the indicator variance contained by its dimensions. The convergence of the AVE value greater than 0.5 also indicates good adequacy of validity for the dimension. On the reflective indicator variable, it can be seen from the average variance extracted (AVE) value for each construct (variable). A good model is required if the AVE value of each construct is greater than 0.5. The test results show that the AVE value for the construct (variable) of Interpersonal Skill, Competency, Commitment and Employee Performance has a value greater than 0.5, so it is valid. Overall, it shows that all indicators on the interpersonal skill variable have a greater AVE square root value than the correlation value with other variables, then the discriminant validity is fulfilled.

Outer Model – Discriminant Validity

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Table 3. Discriminant Validity Testing

Variable	Interpersonal Skills (X1)	Employee Performance (Y)	Commitment (Z)	Competency (X2)
Interpersonal Skills (X1)	0.705	0.503	0.489	0.344
Employee Performance (Y)	0.503	0.638	0.545	0.604
Commitment (Z)	0.489	0.545	0.898	0.491
Competency (X2)	0.344	0.604	0.491	0.704

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The discriminant validity test is to measure how far a construct really differs from other constructs. A high discriminant value provides evidence that a construct is unique and capable of capturing the phenomenon being measured. The way to test it is to compare the square root value of the average variance extracted (AVE) with the correlation value between constructs. Furthermore, discriminant validity testing was carried out with the Fornell-Larcker approach.

In testing discriminant validity, the AVE square root value of an indicator is compared with the correlation value between that indicator and other indicators. It is known that the AVE square root value for each indicator is greater than the correlation value between that indicator and other indicators. For example, the interpersonal skills indicator with four indicators (X1.1, X1.2, X1.3 and X1.4) has an AVE root value of 0.705 which is greater than the correlation value with other variables of 0.503; 0.489 ; 0.344 etc. So that the interpersonal skills indicator is met with discriminant validity. Discriminant validity testing assesses the square of the AVE of a latent variable compared to the correlation value between the latent variable and other latent variables. It is known that the AVE square root value of each latent variable is greater than the correlation value between other latent variables. So it is concluded that it meets discriminant validity.

Outer Model - Reliability Test

Construct reliability is measured by the composite reliability value, the construct is reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.70 then the indicator is called consistent in measuring its latent variables. The test results show that the construct (variable) of Interpersonal Skill, Competency, Commitment and Employee Performance has a composite reliability value of greater than 0.7. so reliable.

Table 4. Reliability Test

Variable	Indicator	CR	ca
Interpersonal Skills	Ability to be open (X1.1)	0.796	0.769
	Tolerance towards others (X1.2)		
	Collaborate with others (X1.3)		
	Ability to provide support to others (X1.4)		
Competence	Value (X2.1)	0.829	0.741
	Self-development (X2.2)		
	Knowledge (X2.3)		
	Skills (X2.4)		
	Professional (X2.5)		
Commitment	Normative commitment (Z1)	0.893	0.761
	Engagement (Z2)		
Performance	Working quantity (Y1)	0.772	0.749
	Quality of work (Y2)		
	Efficient (Y3)		
	Timeliness (Y4)		
	Initiative (Y5)		

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

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Inner Model

Results of the Hypothesis Model

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Figure 2 Bootstrapping Results

Inner Model - Fit Model R2

Testing of the structural model is carried out by looking at the R-Square value which is a goodness-fit model test. Inner model testing can be seen from the R-square value on the equation between latent variables. The value of R2 explains how much the exogenous (independent/independent) variables in the model are able to explain the endogenous (dependent/dependent) variables.

Table 5. R Square

Variable	R Square	R Square Adjusted
Performance (Y)	0.589	0.566
Commitment (Z)	0.357	0.333

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

The value of R2 (Employee Performance) = 0.589, this can be interpreted that the model is able to explain the phenomenon/problem of Employee Performance by 58.90%. While the rest (41.10%) is explained by other variables (besides the Interpersonal Skill, Competency, and Commitment variables) that have not been included in the model and errors.

Predictive Relevance(Q²) or Q-Square measures how well the observed values are generated by the research model. The Q-Square value (Q²) ranges from 0 to 1. Models with predictive validity must have a Q-Squared value greater than 0 (Sholihin and Ratmono, 2020). The closer to the value 1 indicates the observed value produces a better model. Conversely, approaching a value of 0 will produce a bad model. In addition, according to Ghazali and Lathan (2012) the criteria for strong and weak models are based on Q-Square values, namely 0.35 (strong model), 0.15 (moderate model), 0.02 (weak model). The results of this Q-Square calculation are based on known results using warpPLS 6.0 software, namely 0.425 Q-Square values using the Stone-Geisser Q Square Test formula are as follows (Ghozali, 2016):

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - R1) (1 - R2)$$

$$Q2 = 1 - (1 - 0.589) (1 - 0.357)$$

$$Q2 = 0.736$$

The Q-Square value of 0.736 indicates that the model's predictive relevance is 73.60% and the remaining 26.40% is explained by other variables outside this research model and a value of 0.736 is categorized as a strong model, so this research model is suitable for testing hypotheses.

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Inner Model - Causality Test

In partial least squares (PLS) path parameter coefficients are obtained through inner model weights by first finding t-statistical values or p-values through standard error bootstrap procedures, with the calculation results of the Smart PLS software then the path coefficients on the inner weight in this study.

Table 6. Path Coefficient Test and Significance of Influence

	Path Coefficient	P Values	Information
Interpersonal Skill (X1) -> Employee_Performance (Y)_	0.236	0.044	Significant
Commitment (Z) -> Employee_Performance (Y)_	0.163	0.197	Non-significant
Competence (X2) -> Employee_Performance (Y)_	0.543	0.000	Significant

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Based on the results of the inner weight in table 7 it can be concluded:

1. Interpersonal Skill (X1) has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance with a path coefficient of 0.236 where p-values = 0.044 smaller than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H1 is accepted;
2. Competence (X2) has a significant positive effect on Employee Performance with a path coefficient of 0.543 where p-values = 0.000 smaller than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H2 is accepted.

Intervening Variables

Table 7. Mediation Testing

	Path Coefficient	P Values	Information
Interpersonal Skill (X1) -> Commitment (Y) -> Employee_Performance (Y)_	0.059	0.355	Non significant
Competence (X2) -> Commitment (Y) -> Employee_Performance (Y)_	0.060	0.260	Non significant

Source: Primary data processed, 2023

Intervening variables are variables that theoretically influence the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable to become an indirect relationship and cannot be observed and measured.

Where in table 4.18 it can be seen the results of the intervening variables as follows:

1. Interpersonal Skill (X1) has a non-significant effect on employee performance through commitment with a path coefficient of 0.059 where p-values = 0.355 greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H3 is rejected;
2. Competence (X2) has a non-significant effect on Employee Performance through Commitment with a path coefficient of 0.060 where p-values = 0.260 greater than the value of $\alpha = 0.05$ (5%) then H4 is rejected.

VII. IMPLICATIONS OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Interpersonal skills has a significant positive direct effect on employee performance and is considered important based on its composite reliability value, the indicator is called consistent in measuring its latent variables. This means that the value of interpersonal skills possessed by respondents is able to directly improve employee performance even though the level of education possessed by respondents is mostly high school. With the age of the respondent belonging to the middle age category, the skills possessed are standard but do not rule out the possibility of trying new things. This can be influenced by the length of work and the work done is work that is repeated and done every day in accordance with the job description that is owned so that interpersonal skills have been honed every day supported by the trust of the Leaders that those who are elected as non-PNS permanent education staff are the choice. good and has been forged in skill, integrity and loyalty to the institution. This research is supported by the results of research conducted April (2020) which produces interpersonal skills that have a positive effect on employee performance at the Central Bureau of Statistics of Barito Kuala Regency. This is in line with the theory used by researchers according to Storey (1995) that the competitive advantage possessed by respondents is interpersonal skills which are soft skills inherent in each individual.

Competence has a significant positive direct effect on performance. This means that the competence possessed by respondents, whether it is experience from previous work before at Airlangga University or after receiving training from the University, as seen from the previous table related to the amount of training attended, there is still a small proportion of respondents who have not participated in the training because in 2021 he just joined the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment. Respondents who have attended the training are expected to attend foreign language training in order to be able to communicate with stakeholders in multiple languages which is very important and beneficial not only for

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organizations/companies but also for individuals/workers. This research is supported by research Manulang et al. (2020) which produces a relationship of competence to performance has a significant positive effect on employee performance.

Commitment cannot contribute to mediating interpersonal skills on performance. The results of this study contradict the research Nurmalasari, (2019) that interpersonal skill through commitment has a positive effect on performance. And not in line with the theory used by researchers according to Storey, (1995), this means that without commitment, interpersonal skills can increase performance value. In the scattered questionnaires it is known that most of the respondents have normative commitment which indicates that the respondents work on the responsibilities given and it is an obligation to complete the work. This means that most of the positions held by respondents do not require higher education and do not require certain expertise or skills in completing their work, for example a parking attendant whose target is to make the parked vehicles neatly arranged and the vehicles going in and out of and to the parking lot does not collide. Likewise with the printing officer who is on duty every day to check the equipment used then print and the printed results are submitted to the direct superior so that they can enter the realm of production. This activity is repeated every day. Interpersonal skills possessed by respondents are communication skills both verbal and non-verbal and sensitivity to the work environment. The results of this study are supported by the research conducted (Rafika Ningsih et al., 2019) that interpersonal communication has no significant effect on employee performance through the mediation of organizational commitment. In general, high commitment can improve performance but the analysis conditions are not supportive even though the parameters are positive.

Commitment cannot contribute to mediate competency on performance. The results of this study contradict the research Anggraeni & Helmy, (2020) explains that competence through commitment has a positive effect on performance. The high school level of education has the character of being ordered first and then working without any initiative and working according to SOPs. The work carried out takes place continuously which results in no initiative at work being required. If there are problems in the field, asking the direct supervisor can mean that the problem solving has not been resolved by the respondent. The trust of the direct supervisor when they become non-PNS permanent education staff is really maintained because not all education staff at Airlangga University are given the opportunity. The results of this study are supported by the research conducted Rakhmawati (2021) that commitment cannot mediate the influence of competence on performance. And not in line with the theory used by researchers according to Storey, (1995), this means that without commitment, competence can increase performance value. It can be interpreted that there are several educational staff who have not been maximized in the development of self-competence. This can be seen from the results of the questionnaires distributed that there are still non-PNS permanent education staff who have never attended training organized by the Directorate of Human Resources, whether it is related to the lack of training that is in accordance with the existing positions or the non-PNS permanent education staff not being selected for Participate in training provided by the direct supervisor. In this regard, the explanation is as follows:

- 1) Based on the results of research from direct influence which states that both interpersonal skills and competencies are able to contribute to performance, efforts are needed to improve interpersonal skills and competency abilities of non-PNS permanent education staff
- 2) Based on the results of research on indirect influence, commitment is not able to contribute to mediate both interpersonal skills and competencies on performance, it is necessary to change the leadership style from "telling" to "participative" with the aim that non-PNS education staff have the initiative in solving problems while working and creative ideas to improve performance with competent resources towards a competitive international world.

VIII. RESEARCH LIMITATION

Based on direct experience in this research process, there are some limitations that are experienced and can be a number of factors that are more considered by future researchers to perfect the current research because this research has deficiencies that need to be corrected in future research. Some limitations in this study, among others:

1. In the process of collecting data and information provided to respondents through questionnaires that were distributed more completely and completely filled in using a printed questionnaire rather than using a Google form sent via social media.
2. This research is aimed at non-PNS permanent education staff in implementing staff at the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment at Universitas Airlangga, where there are still employees with other statuses such as Temporary Employees and Freelance Daily Workers.
3. The number of respondents is 57 people, of course it still does not describe the actual situation at the Directorate of Logistics, Security, Order and Environment, Universitas Airlangga.

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IX. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Based on the results of the analysis, the following conclusions are obtained:

1. Interpersonal skills able to contribute directly to performance. This indicates that interpersonal skills have an important role in improving the performance of non-PNS permanent education staff.
2. Competence is able to contribute to performance directly. This indicates that competence has an important role in improving the performance of non-PNS permanent education personnel.
3. Commitment cannot contribute to mediating interpersonal skills on performance indirectly. This happens because the work carried out so far has lasted for a period of more than 5 years and tends to have responsibility in carrying out the work.
4. Commitment cannot contribute to mediating competency on performance indirectly. This indicates that the competencies of non-PNS permanent education staff require training in self-competence development.

SUGGESTION

The suggestions that the author can convey on the results of the research that has been carried out are as follows:

1. The ability to provide support to others or empathy needs to be improved with the aim of overcoming work pressure, solving problems, finding new opportunities and motivating oneself or others to achieve institutional goals.
2. Competence that exists in individuals needs to be improved in self-development to support completing work.
3. The normative commitment of non-PNS permanent education staff needs to be increased to a continuous commitment so that loyalty and integrity towards the institution emerges.
4. The efficiency of non-PNS permanent education staff is increased in order to achieve institutional goals.
5. Future researchers are expected to add the variables of leadership, integrity, motivation and work environment to be studied.

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